

A Study of Oxovanadium(IV) Sulphate Complexes^a

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The coordination complexes of the type $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot n\text{L}$ [$n=4$, $\text{L}=\text{thiourea (tu)}$; $n=1$, $\text{L}=\text{phenyl thiourea (Ptu)}$ or $o\text{-chlorophenyl thiourea (o-Cl-Ptu)}$] and $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot n\text{L} \cdot n'\text{L}'$ [$n=2$, $n'=1/2$, $\text{L}=\text{pyridine (py)}$, $\text{L}'=\text{tu}$; $n=4$, $n'=1$, $\text{L}=\text{py}$, $\text{L}'=\text{Ptu}$; $n=1$, $n'=1/2$, $\text{L}=\text{py}$, $\text{L}'=o\text{-Cl-Ptu}$ or $\text{benzoyl thiourea (bztu)}$] are synthesized. The complexes are characterized by infrared, electronic and ESR spectra and magnetic susceptibility studies. The effect of electron donor ligands such as py on νVO and the behaviour of SO_4 as a bidentate chelating group are also discussed. The spin orbit coupling constant (λ) and other parameters $g_{\parallel}$, $g_{\perp}$, $A_{\parallel}$ and $A_{\perp}$ are calculated from the ESR spectral data. The correlation between delocalizing of π antibonding, the extent of covalence of metal ligand bond and also the criterion for the inverted order of levels [$g(^2E) > b_1(^2B_2)$] in the octahedral complexes are suggested from these parameters.

INFORMATION on thiourea complexes of oxovanadium(IV) is lacking. In view of this, infrared, electronic and ESR spectral and magnetic susceptibility data of some of these complexes are presented in this paper. Purposeful conclusions are drawn regarding metal ligand bonding, covalency and structural features.

(4000-400 cm^{-1}) and Beckmann IR-12 (650-200 cm^{-1}) spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded on Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer for powdered samples and Carl-Zeiss IMR-21 instrument for mull samples. EPR spectra of powdered samples at 27° were obtained using a Varian E-4 X-band EPR spectrometer at 9.45 GHz frequency using DPPH free-radical as g marker.

Experimental

Vanadyl sulphate, thiourea and phenyl thiourea were of reagent grade. *o*-Chlorophenyl thiourea and benzoyl thiourea were prepared by standard methods^{1,2}.

Preparation of complexes : (i) The monoligand complexes were synthesized by mixing $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the thiourea ligand in ethanol and refluxing for about 15 hr. The resulting greenish blue or blue solution was concentrated and the solid was crystallized with or without the aid of chloroform in case of tu or Ptu, respectively. The solid was washed with ethanol-chloroform mixture or ethanol and dried in vacuum.

(ii) A hot mixture of thiourea and pyridine (1:1 ratio) was added to VOSO_4 solution with constant stirring. This resulted in the formation of a green coloured mixed ligand complex which settled on cooling in ice (4°). The product was collected, washed and dried in vacuum.

The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents.

Analysis : The complexes were analysed for vanadium, nitrogen and sulphur by standard methods³.

Physical measurements : Infrared spectral measurements were made on Perkin-Elmer 337

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis of the complexes are shown in Table 1. The table also records the stoichiometric composition of the complexes. The complexes appear to be quite stable as they do not show any tendency of decomposition.

Infrared spectra : Infrared spectral frequencies along with their assignments for the major peaks pertaining to the various complexes are shown in Table 2.

In the complexes I and IV, coordination occurs only through nitrogen as indicated by (i) a negative shift of the order of 10-100 cm^{-1} in νNH and of 20-40 cm^{-1} in bands A (1600-1650 cm^{-1}) and B (1600-1400 cm^{-1}) and (ii) a positive shift in band G ($\sim 690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In the complexes V to VII, the thiocarbonyl sulphur and pyridine nitrogen have taken part in bond formation as shown by (i) a registered positive shift of the order 10-70 cm^{-1} in νNH vibrations, (ii) a positive shift of the order 5-40 cm^{-1} in bands A and B and (iii) a negative shift of the order 7-16 cm^{-1} in the band G. The metal pyridine coordination has been established in complexes IV-VII by the observed shift to higher frequencies of those at 604 cm^{-1} (in plane ring deformation) and 405 cm^{-1} (out of plane ring deformation) – the positive shift being 20-50 and $\sim 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$,

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) SULPHATE COMPLEXES WITH THIOUREAS

Complex No.	Composition	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		
				V	N	S
I	VOSO ₄ .4tu	Blue	120	10.88 (10.90)	24.01 (23.96)	34.24 (34.27)
II	VOSO ₄ .Ptu	Greenish blue	>300	16.21 (16.15)	8.91 (8.88)	20.43 (20.34)
III	VOSO ₄ .o-Cl-Ptu	"	>300	14.53 (14.56)	8.07 (8.01)	18.08 (18.94)
IV	[VOSO ₄ .2py.½tu] ₂	Black green	>280	14.21 (14.18)	11.75 (11.70)	13.41 (13.39)
V	[2VOSO ₄ .Ptu.4py]	Dark green	95	14.61 (14.58)	12.15 (12.02)	9.31 (9.18)
VI	[VOSO ₄ .½o-Cl-Ptu.py] ₂	Green	>280	15.31 (15.02)	8.51 (8.32)	14.35 (14.34)
VII	[VOSO ₄ .py.½Bztu] ₂	"	160	15.22 (15.33)	8.44 (8.43)	14.51 (14.43)

TABLE 2—INFRARED FREQUENCIES (in cm⁻¹) OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) SULPHATE COMPLEXES WITH THIOUREAS (in KBr)

Compound	νNH	νC=O	Ring str. of pyridine	δNH ₂ A	ν _{asy} NCN + δNH ₂ B	νC-S G	νM-S	νM-N	νV=O	δpy in plane	δpy out of plane	κV=O m dynes/A
tu*	3370 m br 3267 m br 3160 m br	-	-	1612 s	1470 s	630 m br	-	-	-	-	-	-
I	3362 m br 3250 m br 3150 m br	-	-	1600 ms	1432 s	632 w	-	482 br	968 m br	-	-	6.71
Ptu	3394 m s 3247 m s 3150 m s	-	-	1608 s	1515 ms	640 m s	-	-	-	-	-	-
II	3405 s 3195 m br 3086 m br	-	-	1630 w	1450 s	622 vw	376 m s	548 s	992 m br	-	-	7.21
o-Cl-Ptu	3335 m s 3250 m br 3154 m s	-	-	1602 s	1540 s	630 m s	-	-	-	-	-	-
III	3424 s 3205 s 3087 m br	-	-	1625 sh	1449 s	624 m s	382 m s	548 s	992 m br	-	-	6.74
tu	3372 m br 3270 m br 3170 m br	-	-	1620 s	1470 s	623 612 br	-	-	-	-	-	-
IV	3450 vw 3300 vw 3220 vw 3070 vw	-	1610 sh 1450 s	1635 ms	1480*	625- 612 w sh	-	520 br	970 br	620 m s	450 m s	6.74
Ptu	3394 m s 3247 m s 3150 m s	-	-	1608 s	1515 ms	640 s	-	-	-	-	-	-
V	3425 m s 3272 m br 3175 m s	-	1608 vs 1485 s	1608 vs+	1520 s	630 m s	453 m s	490 ms	967 br	620 m s	450 m s	6.56
o-Cl-Ptu	3335 m s 3250 m br 3154 m s	-	-	1602 s	1540 s	630 m s	-	-	-	-	-	-
VI	3420 w 3341 br 3250 br 3162 w	-	1610 vs 1532 w	1651 vs	1552 ms	630 m s	420 w	523 m s	965 br	625 w	443 m s	6.68
Bztu	3272 m s 3190 m s 3120 m s	1674 s	-	1595 s	1527 ms	663 m s	-	-	-	-	-	-
VII	3345 m br 3230 w 3070 m s	1680 m s	1604 ms 1480 s	1604 ms+	1540 m br	656 m s	457 w	534 m s	950 br	650 m s	457 m br	6.46

Ring stretching vibrations of pyridine occur at 1599 sh, 1583 s, 1482 s and 1441 s cm⁻¹. * in nujol mull.
*Overlapped with pyridine vibration.

TABLE 3—DIFFUSED ELECTRONIC DATA (cm⁻¹), MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ESR PARAMETERS OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) SULPHATE COMPLEXES WITH THIOUREAS

Complex No.	² B ₂ → ² E	² B ₂ → ² B ₁	² B ₂ → ² A ₁	Dq	D _s	D _t	μ_{eff} B.M.	ESR Parameters			λ Calcd.	A _⊥ × 10 ⁻⁴ cm ⁻¹	A _∥ × 10 ⁻⁴ cm ⁻¹	$\Delta g_{\perp} / \Delta g_{\parallel}$
								g _⊥	g _∥	g _s				
I	12200	15880	19230	1588	-2221.4	1107.2	2.44	1.973	2.087	2.011	220.0 282.1	-148.5	-46.4	2.85
II	12120	16000	23180	1600	-2718.4	792.8	1.98	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
III	12270	16000	21780	1600	-2571.4	911.2	2.395	1.983	2.035	2.000	146.1	-139	-38.5	2.38
IV	10180	18180	22220	1818	-2121.4	889.2	1.88	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
V	11630	16940	22260	1694	-2564.3	787.4	1.224	1.986	2.041	2.004	113.3 117.0	-143	-50	1.69
VI	11110	17390	22990	1739	-2386	790.4	1.43	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
VII	11760	18180	22220	1818	-2257	999.8	1.12	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

respectively. Similar observations have been made by Clark and Williams⁶ for their metal-pyridine complexes. For complexes II and III, chelate formation by coordination through nitrogen as well as sulphur is indicated by (i) a negative shift of the order 50-80 cm⁻¹ in the symmetric vibration of NH₂ group (ν NH) and the order of 65-95 cm⁻¹ in band B, (ii) a positive shift of the order 60-70 cm⁻¹ in band A with reduced intensity and (iii) a negative shift of the order 6-65 cm⁻¹ in the band G.

The bands observed in the region 370-457 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν M-S vibration and those corresponding to 480-550 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν M-N vibration for the present complexes.

In complexes IV-VII, the data obtained from ir spectra and the chemical analysis enable us to ensure that thiourea and its derivatives may be acting as bridging units between two vanadyl species. In accordance with the observations of Morgan⁵ and Rivest⁷ we suggest that tu acts as a bridge through two different NH₂ groups or through S in complexes IV and V-VII, respectively.

The VO (1000 cm⁻¹) is quite sensitive to the nature of *trans* ligand and donors which cause lowering of ν VO. Studies on such lengthening of the V=O bond by *trans* coordination have been reported by Selbin⁸ and Datta *et al.*⁹

From the ir spectral data it is concluded that sulphate acts as a bidentate chelating group in case of complexes II, III, V and VI due to the splitting of ν_3 (~1160 cm⁻¹) and ν_4 (~600 cm⁻¹) sulphate bands into doublets and triplets¹⁰.

Electronic spectra: The diffused reflectance spectra of complexes I to III¹¹ reveal band I as a broad band of high intensity whereas II and III appear as weak bands or shoulders. In the other four complexes all the three appear as weak bands and are not well developed. The appearance of undeveloped bands is characteristic of electronic spectra of subnormal oxovanadium complexes¹². Further, the more intense band (10000 to 12000 cm⁻¹) is assigned to the first transition ²E ← ²B₂. Thus, the nature of electronic spectra support our view that the present vanadyl complexes are tetragonal, distorted and probably possessing C_{4v} symmetry.

Paul and coworkers¹³ also observed bands in the same region for the adducts of oxovanadium(IV). The Dq, D_s and D_t values comes to 1518 to 1818, -2121 to -2571 and 790 to 1107 cm⁻¹, respectively. These values agree well with the values reported by other investigators^{13,14} for similar complexes of C_{4v} symmetry.

The observed higher μ_{eff} value (1.88 to 2.51 B.M.) compared to spin only value 1.73 B.M.) suggests the presence of some spin orbit interaction of vanadium ion in the complex (Table 3). The lower value (1.12-1.43 B.M.) in some other complexes may lead to their involvement in magnetic exchange¹⁴.

ESR spectra: The vanadyl sulphate mixed complex derived from the ligands phenyl thiourea and pyridine exhibits distinct eight hyperfine lines. While the tu complex shows some splitting, the *o*-Cl-Ptu complex does not show the splitting. The latter is characteristic of weak coordination of the ligand (Cf ir spectra and V=O stretching). The g_⊥ and g_∥ values are assigned by judicious selection of average position. The spin orbit coupling constant, λ , and other parameters A_⊥ and A_∥ are calculated according to the procedure of Assour¹⁵ and are tabulated (Table 3).

It appears that the delocalizing of in plane π antibonding and out of plane π antibonding increases in the order of covalence of the metal ligand bond which is shown by increase in spin-orbit coupling constant. Further, a tentative criterion for the inverted order of levels [eg(²E) above b₂ (²B₂)] in our complexes can be correlated to the ratio $\Delta g_{\parallel} / \Delta g_{\perp}$ being 2.37 i.e. less than 4.

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